

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF LEARNERS' BEHAVIOR ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHING PERFORMANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

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The Mediating Effect of Learners' Behavior on the Relationship Between Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of learners' behavior on the correlation between teaching performance and job satisfaction among public school teachers among 124 learners and 75 public school teachers from five different schools in the Municipality of Maitum. In selecting the respondents, Slovin's formula was used for the learner respondents, while total enumeration was used for the teacher respondents. Moreover, quantitative design utilizing descriptive correlation techniques was employed in the study. Findings revealed that the level of teaching performance of teachers was very high in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, high in learning environment, high in diversity of learners, very high in curriculum and planning, very high in assessment and reporting, high in community linkages and professional engagement, and very high in personal growth and professional development. Additionally, the level of job satisfaction of teachers was high in terms of security, high in work environment, very high in job responsibilities, and very high in community attachments/linkages. Also, the extent of learner's behavior was manifested most of the time in terms of competence motivation, while manifested occasionally in terms of strategy/flexibility. The study identified significant relationships between teaching performance and job satisfaction, teaching performance and learners' behavior, as well as learners' behavior and job satisfaction. Notably, learners' behavior was found to mediate the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction, albeit partially.

Keywords: *educational management, learner's behavior, teaching performance, job satisfaction, mediating effect*

Introduction

Job satisfaction is a pervasive issue that affects individuals and organizations on a large scale. It refers to the contentment and fulfillment employees experience in their work environment. When job satisfaction is low, it can have far-reaching consequences, including decreased productivity, increased turnover rates, and a decline in overall well-being. Several key factors contribute to this global problem. One critical aspect of job satisfaction is work-life balance. Maintaining a healthy balance between work and personal life is essential in today's fast-paced world. Employees facing long working hours, excessive workloads, and a lack of flexibility can lead to stress and dissatisfaction. Finding time for personal pursuits, relationships, and self-care can harm job satisfaction (Masrom et al., 2021).

Additionally, satisfied employees tend to perform better in their roles. Employees who are content with their jobs become more engaged, motivated, and committed. The heightened dedication translates into higher productivity, improved work productivity, and increased efficiency. Satisfied employees often go above and beyond their job requirements, leading to better outcomes for themselves and their organization. Furthermore, job satisfaction plays a vital role in employee retention. Longer tenure in an organization is associated with employee satisfaction, reducing turnover rates. Organizations may incur significant costs due to high turnover because of the costs of recruitment, training, and onboarding new employees (Imron et al., 2020).

On the other hand, job satisfaction in education carries significant national implications that extend beyond individual teachers and schools. When teachers are satisfied with their jobs, teacher retention rates are enhanced, ensuring stability and continuity within the education system. Moreover, job satisfaction is crucial in teacher performance and professional development. Satisfied teachers are more inclined to actively seek growth opportunities, engage in professional development programs, and continuously enhance their instructional skills. This ongoing professional growth contributes to the overall improvement of the education system, benefiting the students and the nation (Baluyos et al., 2019).

However, despite the extensive research on teaching performance and job satisfaction, more in-depth exploration is needed regarding the specific influence of learners' behavior on this relationship. While studies have examined the impact of various factors on teaching performance and job satisfaction, such as instructional practices, administrative support, and organizational culture, the role of learners' behavior still needs to be studied more. Understanding this dynamic could provide valuable insights for enhancing both teaching effectiveness and job satisfaction. Therefore, future research should prioritize investigating how learners' behavior influences these outcomes. Thus, the urgency of studying the learner's behavior about teaching performance and job satisfaction extends beyond the individual level. It has practical significance for the overall quality of education and the well-being of teachers. By recognizing the urgency and investing in research on learner behavior, educational institutions can create environments that promote positive behavior, effective teaching, and job satisfaction. In turn, it can lead to improved student outcomes, increased teacher retention, and the overall enhancement of the education system. The researcher conducted this study to determine the mediating effect of learner's behavior on the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction of public-school teachers in Maitum East District. Furthermore,

this study will determine whether significant relationships between variables will exist.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of learners' behavior on the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction of public school teachers. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. Determine the level of teaching performance of public school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. content, knowledge, and pedagogy;
 - 1.2. learning environment;
 - 1.3. diversity of learners
 - 1.4. curriculum and planning;
 - 1.5. assessment and reporting;
 - 1.6. community linkages and professional engagement, and
 - 1.7. personal growth and professional development.
2. Determine the level of job satisfaction of public school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. security;
 - 2.2. work environment;
 - 2.3. job responsibilities, and
 - 2.4. community attachments/linkages.
3. Determine the common extent of manifestation of learners' behavior in terms of;
 - 3.1. Competence, motivation, and
 - 3.2. Strategy/flexibility.
4. Determine the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1. teaching performance and job satisfaction;
 - 4.2. teaching performance and learners' behavior, and
 - 4.3. learners' behavior and job satisfaction of public-school teachers;
5. Determine the significance of mediation of learners' behavior on the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction of Public School Teachers.

Methodology

This section discusses the methods employed in this study, including research design, research locale, population and sample, research instruments used to measure constructs of interest, data collection procedures, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative nonexperimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research. It was designed to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. In nonexperimental research, researchers collect data without making changes or introducing treatments. In this study, the variables were not manipulated, and the setting was not in control (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

In addition, an approach to quantitative research is described by a quantitative research design. It seeks to ascertain the population's size for a given belief, action, or feeling. Large sample sizes are often used in quantitative projects since the focus is on the number of responses rather than the deeper or more emotional understanding that qualitative research seeks to elicit. In a quantitative research design, the same questions are often asked of each respondent to guarantee that the entire data sample can be thoroughly investigated. Furthermore, the data is presented numerically, facilitating quantitative statistical analysis (Rahman, 2020).

Moreover, in quantitative research, closed-ended questions are frequently preferred. The need to give the respondents a predetermined list of options to provide in-depth, open-ended responses. This design ensures that the quantitative research process is much more effective than if open-ended questions of the qualitative type were used. It is more effective because it eliminates the need for the time-consuming task of coding a sizable number of open-ended responses. However, when appropriate, the quantitative research design frequently permits the inclusion of an "Other" category in the list of possible answers to questions. As a result, respondents who do not directly fit into the major categories can still have their accurate responses recorded and used to analyze the research findings (Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the quantitative research design aims to gather and extrapolate numerical data to other demographics. This design makes every detail well thought out and planned before the data collection. The researcher also has a well-defined research topic that is being answered objectively. Data include things like numbers and statistics. Projects can be used to look into causal linkages, forecast results, or, in a broader sense, generalize ideas (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

On the other hand, a correlational study is a type of research design that examines the relationship between two or more variables. With correlational research, a nonexperimental research technique, two variables are measured, and the statistical relationship between them

is understood and assessed independently of any other variable. Since correlational investigations are nonexperimental, no variables are altered or under the experimenter's control (Seeram, 2019).

Similarly, descriptive-correlation research design explains and analyzes the world around us, shedding light on genuine and imagined relationships and situations. Additionally, because it is a fact-finding study, the researcher can look at the study participants' traits, actions, and experiences. Research is correlational since it investigated the relationship among the variables such as learner's behavior, teaching performance, and job satisfaction. The survey questionnaire is used to gather the data. The interest of the study was to investigate the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction, the relationship between teaching performance and learners' behavior, the relationship between learners' behavior and job satisfaction, and the mediating effect of learners' behavior on the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction of public-school teachers in Maitum East District.

Likewise, mediation analysis is always a concern with causal relations between variables. In complete mediation, the independent variable (X) causes the mediator (M), and M, in turn, causes the dependent variable (Y). In partial mediation, there are both direct and indirect effects of X on Y. There is a growing interest in studying mediation as a research topic due to the importance of doing so for theoretical accounts of causal mechanisms and the strict guidelines associated with research design when dealing with cause-effect relationships in which the mediator provides an explanatory account. Many different designs concentrate on mediators, including nonexperimental (cross-sectional or longitudinal) and experimental (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Participants

This study's respondents were 180 learners and 75 public school teachers from 5 different schools in the Municipality of Maitum. Total enumeration was applied to obtain the desired population of teacher respondents, while Slovin's Formula was utilized to obtain the population of learners. From the original population of 180, the final population of learners was only 124.

Slovin's Formula is a statistical method for calculating the sample size needed for a survey or study based on the size of the population being studied and the desired level of precision. The formula is often used in Social Science research to determine the minimum number of respondents needed to ensure that a study's results represent the population as a whole (Ismail et al., 2022).

The table below shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

School	Number of Respondents		
	Learners		Teachers
	N	n	
Kiayap Elementary School	30	20	9
Maitum Elementary School	30	20	13
Malalag Central ES SPED Center	60	41	41
Pangi Elementary School	30	22	9
Sison Elementary School	30	22	10
TOTAL	180	124	75

Instruments

Three questionnaires were adopted from different authors and used in this study. The instrument focused on learners' behavior, teaching behavior, and job satisfaction.

Questionnaire for Learners' Behavior. A questionnaire was used to determine the level of learners' behavior. It is based on the study of Chao et al. (2018). It is composed of 2 indicators. The first indicator is competence motivation, which is composed of 14 statements. The second indicator is strategy/flexibility, which comprises ten statements.

Questionnaire for Teaching Performance. This questionnaire was used to determine the level of teaching performance. It is based on the standardized Key Results Area (KRA) of the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) for teachers. This instrument consists of four indicators: content knowledge and pedagogy, learning atmosphere and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting. The teachers were instructed and guided to check the box according to the column appropriate to their choice, and all items should be answered.

Questionnaire for Job Satisfaction. This questionnaire was used to determine job satisfaction among public school teachers in the Maitum East District. It was adapted from the Job Satisfaction Level of K12 Teachers Utilizing Multiple Statistical Tools by Romero and Bantigue (2017). It comprises four indicators: security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachments/linkages. All indicators are composed of 10 statements each.

Data Collection

The researcher collected the data based on the book of Aguinis et al. (2021) entitled "Fundamental of Research Methodology and Data Collection." Before conducting the study, one of the researcher's responsibilities was approaching the organization and requesting

permission. If the organization has specific policies regarding the research activities, the necessary steps should be followed to ensure that the study is conducted ethically and with validity. One of the initial steps was to develop research questions that validators would then validate. Once the research questions were validated, the researcher sought approval from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to ensure that the study would be conducted ethically. After obtaining approval from the committee, the researcher proceeded to seek permission from the Dean of the institution and the Schools Division Superintendent of Sarangani Province.

Once permission was granted, the researcher requested the participation of individuals willing to participate in the study and provided them with an Informed Consent Form. The researcher distributed the questionnaires and was ready to respond immediately to any respondents' queries. There was an ample time for the instructor respondents to finish the questionnaire. The researcher collected the results, combined them, and used statistical analysis for data interpretation.

Item analysis was performed on the retrieved questionnaires to identify the components with the greatest and lowest contributions to the indicator's overall mean. This analysis helped to pinpoint specific areas of strength and weakness within the dataset. As a result, we gained valuable insights into which components most significantly influenced the overall performance indicator.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor has specific ramifications. These problems and worries can primarily result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research are concerned on the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration adhered to in this study, especially when it came to the populace and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were given the choice to participate in the study voluntarily, and their decision to participate would not result in any negative consequences, compensation loss, or loss of benefits. Before their involvement, the purpose and potential benefits of the study were thoroughly explained to them, ensuring their informed consent and protection of their rights as participants. The subjects were not forced or coerced into participating, and they had the freedom to withdraw from the study if they felt uncomfortable or wished to discontinue their involvement.

Privacy and confidentiality. By the current Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy, respondents have a right to privacy that should not be infringed upon without their informed agreement. One method for preserving privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study is to allow the respondents not to include their names on the survey form. Furthermore, confidentiality and privacy were achieved by hiding the informants' demographic data, including their age, gender, occupation, and medical condition. Because of this, their identity was concealed for security purposes. Their responses to the survey's questions were kept secret and handled accordingly.

Informed consent process. The potential research participants were as well informed as possible within the study's parameters on the research objectives, procedures, and rewards. A written agreement was obtained from the respondents, proving that they agreed to participate voluntarily. The informed consent form, which the respondents completed, states that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. There is no need to obtain parental permission because the responders are consenting adults. The survey form did not include the names of the respondents, and their answers were kept confidential. The participants knew they might opt out of the study at any time.

Furthermore, the researcher would keep any data they collected private. Any information released would be subject to a rigorous informed consent procedure. The participants would have control over their personal information to decrease their concern that the data or information would be utilized in any other undesired way.

Recruitment. The study's subjects were told of their motivations for participating. The researcher outlined the study's objectives so the respondents could draw further conclusions and grasp its main points. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the purpose and importance of the study.

Risks. If there was a reasonable positive benefit-risk ratio, research was done. It is equally important for this investigation that the participants are shielded from severe damage. The welfare of the respondents was prioritized in the study. The respondents were also unharmed because their identities were kept secret. Their safety and security are our top priorities. As the researcher, ensure the respondents are emotionally, physically, and socially prepared. There was no evidence of uneasiness or awkwardness among the respondents of the study.

Benefits. The outcomes of this study helped the respondents by enhancing their academic performance through radio-based instruction. Therefore, this study aims to aid public elementary teachers, particularly the students. Additionally, to do beneficent research, the researcher must take all reasonable precautions to protect the respondents' well-being and advance relevant research projects. The growth of meaningful learning is the most critical factor in attaining benefits.

Plagiarism. The study has no trace or evidence of misinterpretation of someone else's work. It was subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly. A researcher requires to have integrity and good moral character, which come with moral principles and ideals. In addition, to produce a respectable research report, the researcher needs to be more knowledgeable about plagiarism.

Fabrication. The study lacked any clues or indicators of intentional misinterpretation of what had been done. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes, nor was there any deliberate promotion of false conclusions. Conversely, the researcher used integrated hypotheses relating to the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not intentionally exaggerate or mislead the work to satisfy a model or theoretical assumption. Additionally, this study did not adhere to data manipulation, which entailed creating assertions or omitting crucial information, as well as rearranging materials, instruments, or procedures in a way that would deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). Conflicts of interest (COI) are situations in which professional judgment about primary claims like participants' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest like financial or academic gains or recognitions. The study had no traces of COI, such as the disclosure of COI. Furthermore, the researcher has no authority or control over the respondents, forced them to participate in the survey.

Deceit. There was no evidence that the study misled the respondents about potential risks. The rights of everybody who participated in an investigation are fiercely protected, especially if they have completed higher education. Therefore, reasonable and suitable standards are followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's research adhered to procedures. The researcher requested permission from the school's division superintendent for the study through a written letter after receiving the go-ahead from the panelists, adviser, and committee of the RMMCERC. After that, the researcher drafted a formal letter addressed to the district supervisor and school principal of the participating schools, attached a letter that the division superintendent of the school had endorsed. Before distributing the survey questionnaire, the public elementary school teachers who participated in the study received an orientation.

Results

This section presents the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in the study.

3.1. The Level of Teaching Performance of Public School Teachers in Terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 2 presents the data on public school teachers' teaching performance regarding content, knowledge, and pedagogy. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the level of teaching performance was very high, with an overall mean of 4.6. It suggests that teachers excel in their teaching practices. They effectively apply their knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas, with a mean score of 4.6. Furthermore, teachers demonstrate the application of research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to improve their professional practice, reflected by a mean score of 4.68. They display proficient use of the Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English languages to facilitate effective teaching and learning, as indicated by a mean score of 4.55. Teachers also employed effective verbal and non-verbal classroom methods to support the learners' understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement, receiving a mean score of 4.6. Moreover, they skillfully utilize various teaching strategies to foster critical and creative thinking and other higher-order thinking skills, with a mean score of 4.65.

Table 2. The Level of Teaching Performance of Public School Teachers in Terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

<i>Content, Knowledge and Pedagogy</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching concepts.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Used research-based knowledge and fundamentals of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	4.68	Strongly Agree
Displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to enable teaching and learning.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Used effective verbal and non-verbal classroom strategies to support learner understanding, involvement, engagement, and achievement.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Apply various teaching methods to develop critical and creative ideas and other higher-order thinking skills.	4.65	Strongly Agree
Display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Use effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication methods to support learner understanding, participation, engagement and achievement.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Total	5.60	Strongly Agree

3.2. The Level of Teaching performance in terms of Learning Environment

Table 3 presents the data on the level of teaching performance of public-school teachers in terms of learning environment. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data revealed a high level of teaching performance among public school teachers, particularly in creating a conducive learning environment, with an overall mean of 4.54. It suggests that teachers consistently establish safe and secure learning environments by diligently implementing policies, guidelines, and procedures, as reflected by a mean score of 4.8. They maintain learning environments that foster fairness, respect, and care to promote an atmosphere conducive to learning, earning a mean score of 4.3. Teachers skillfully

control the classroom structure to engage students in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within various physical learning contexts, achieving a mean score of 4.5. Moreover, they sustain supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learners, encouraging active participation, cooperation, and collaboration in continued learning, with a mean score of 4.4. Teachers apply a range of practical strategies that motivate learners to work productively, assuming responsibility for their learning, as indicated by a mean score of 4.6. Additionally, they manage the learners' behavior constructively by employing positive and non-violent discipline approaches, ensuring learning-focused environments, as reflected by a mean score of 4.55.

Table 3. The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Learning Environment

<i>Learning Environment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Established safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning by consistently implementing policies, guidelines and procedures.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Maintained learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	4.3	Agree
Manage classroom structure to engage pupils, individually or in groups, in meaningful journeys, discovery, and hands-on activities within a scope of physical learning environments.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Maintain a supportive learning atmosphere that nurtures and inspires learners to engage, cooperate, and collaborate in continued learning.	4.4	Agree
Apply a range of successful methods that maintain an atmosphere of learning that motivates learners to work productively by requiring them to assume responsibility for their learning.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Manage learner behavior constructively by applying good and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Total	4.54	Strongly Agree

3.3. The level of Teaching Performance in terms of Diversity of Learners

Table 4 presents the data on the level of teaching performance of public-school teachers in terms of diversity of learners. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the level of teaching performance of public-school teachers was high, as shown by the overall mean of 4.26. It suggests that they employed differentiated and developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, individual needs, strengths, interests, and experiences, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.2. Teachers established a learner-centered culture by utilizing teaching strategies responsive to learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds, receiving a mean score of 4.1. Furthermore, they design, adapt, and implement teaching strategies that accommodate the specific needs of the learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents, reflecting a mean score of 4.5. In addition, educators design and implement lesson plans that consider students' unique learning requirements under challenging situations, such as remote locations, long-term illnesses, armed conflict-related relocation, urban resettlement, natural catastrophes, child labor, and abuse, attaining a mean score of 3.9. Furthermore, they adapt and employ culturally appropriate teaching methods to address the unique needs of the learners from indigenous groups, receiving a mean score of 4.6.

Overall, these findings underscore the commitment and effectiveness of public-school teachers in implementing inclusive and responsive teaching practices to ensure quality education for all learners, regardless of their social backgrounds or circumstances.

Table 4. The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Diversity of Learners

<i>Learning Environment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Use differentiated, developmentally, appropriate learning encounters to address learners' gender, needs, advantages, interests, and experiences.	4.2	Agree
Establish a learner-centered culture using teaching strategies that respond to students linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds.	4.1	Agree
Design, adapt and implement teaching strategies responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Plan and deliver teaching methods that are responsive to those special educational needs of pupils under challenging situations, including geographic landscape, chronic sickness, child abuse, child labor practices, urban resettlement after disasters, and displacement brought on by armed conflict.	3.9	Agree
Adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching methods to address the needs of learners from native communities.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Total	4.26	Agree

3.4. The Level of Teaching performance in terms of Curriculum and Planning

Table 5 presents the data on public school teachers' teaching performance regarding curriculum and planning. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that public school teachers' teaching performance in curriculum and planning was very high, as shown by the overall mean of 4.75. It suggests that teachers adeptly organized, oversaw, and carried out developmentally appropriate teaching and learning procedures to satisfy the curriculum requirements. In diverse teaching contexts, an impressive mean score of 4.8 was demonstrated. Teachers demonstrated their expertise by setting achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that align with learning competencies,

earning a high mean score of 4.75. By putting in place the learning systems that guarantee relevance and reactivity to the needs of all learners, they demonstrate adaptability, attaining an exceptional mean score of 4.8. Moreover, teachers actively engage in collegial discussions, leveraging teacher and learner feedback to enrich their teaching practices, as reflected by a commendable mean score of 4.7. They exhibit proficiency in selecting, developing, organizing, and utilizing appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT (Information and Communication Technology), to effectively address the learning goals, achieving a remarkable mean score of 4.8.

Table 5. The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Curriculum and Planning

<i>Learning Environment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Plan, manage, and implement developmentally ordered teaching and learning processes to combine curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes aligned with learning competencies.	4.75	Strongly Agree
Adapt and implement learning programs that ensure relevance and reactivity to the needs of the learners.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Participate in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice.	4.7	Strongly Agree
To meet learning goals, select, develop, organize, and employ appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Total	4.75	Strongly Agree

3.4. The level of Teaching Performance in terms of Assessment and Reporting

Table 6 presents the data on public school teachers' teaching performance regarding assessment and reporting. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that public school teachers' teaching performance in assessment and reporting was very high, as shown by the overall mean of 4.59. It indicates that public school teachers consistently demonstrate excellent performance in assessment practices. They expertly design, select, organize, and utilize diagnostic, formative, and summative evaluation methods that align with the curriculum requirements, as evidenced by an impressive mean score of 4.6. Teachers diligently monitor and evaluate the learners' progress and achievement, utilizing the learners' attainment data to inform their assessments, resulting in a high mean score of 4.54. They employ effective strategies for providing timely, accurate, and constructive feedback to improve the learners' performance, achieving an outstanding mean score of 4.75. Teachers also prioritize clear and prompt communication of learners' needs, progress, and achievement to critical stakeholders, including the parents/guardians, as reflected by a commendable mean score of 4.6. Furthermore, they utilize assessment data to modify teaching and learning practices and programs, demonstrating their commitment to data-driven decision-making and earning a notable mean score of 4.5. Overall, these findings highlight the consistent excellence of public-school teachers in assessment and reporting practices, contributing to quality education outcomes.

Table 6. The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Assessment and Reporting

<i>Assessment and Reporting</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
Design, choose, organize, and use diagnostic, formative, and summative evaluation strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement using learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	4.54	Strongly Agree
Use strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive, feedback to improve learner performance.	4.75	Strongly Agree
Communicate the learners needs, progress and achievements promptly and clearly to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Utilize assessment data to modify teaching and learning practices and programs.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Total	4.59	Strongly Agree

3.5. The Level of Teaching performance in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Table 7 presents the data on public school teachers' teaching performance regarding community linkages and professional engagement. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that public school teachers' level of teaching performance in terms of community linkages and professional engagement was high, as shown by the overall mean of 3.8. It indicates that public school teachers consistently exceed expectations in various areas of their professional practice. They maintain learning environments responsive to community contexts, achieving a mean score of 3.8. They actively build strong connections with parents/guardians and the wider school community, facilitating their involvement in the educative process, as evidenced by an impressive mean score of 4.5. Teachers demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement by regularly reviewing their teaching practice, ensuring alignment with existing laws, regulations, and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, receiving a mean score of 3.4. Moreover, they consistently comply with and implement school policies and procedures, fostering harmonious relationships with the learners, parents, and other stakeholders, as reflected by a mean score of 3.5.

Table 7. The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

<i>Community Linkages and Professional Engagement</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
Maintain learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	3.8	Agree
Build a connection with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate participation in the educative process.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Review personal teaching strategies regularly, using existing laws, and regulations for the teaching profession and the obligation specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.	3.4	Agree
Comply with and implement school regulations and methods consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents and other stakeholders.	3.5	Agree
Total	3.8	Agree

3.6. The Level of Teaching performance in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development

Table 8 presents the data on public school teachers' teaching performance regarding personal growth and professional development. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data analysis revealed exceptional teaching performance among public school teachers regarding personal growth and professional development, with an overall mean score of 4.62. Teachers demonstrated excellent performance in various aspects. They exhibited a learner-centered approach by applying a personal philosophy of teaching ($\bar{x} = 4.8$). Additionally, teachers upheld the dignity of the teaching profession by embodying qualities such as a caring attitude, respect, and integrity ($\bar{x} = 4.5$). They actively engaged in professional networks to share knowledge and enhance their practice ($\bar{x} = 4.5$). Moreover, teachers committed to ongoing professional growth by developing personal and professional improvement plans through reflective practice and continuous learning ($\bar{x} = 4.9$). Their professional development goals were aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers ($\bar{x} = 4.62$).

Table 8. *The Level of Teaching Performance in Terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development*

<i>Personal Growth and Professional Development</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
Apply a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner centered.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Adopt strategies that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting a caring attitude, respect, and integrity.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Participate in professional networks to share knowledge and enhance practice.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Develop a personal professional improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning.	4.9	Strongly Agree
Set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.	4.4	Agree
Total	4.62	Strongly Agree

3.7. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in terms of security

Table 9 presents the level of job satisfaction of public-school teachers in terms of security. The data gathered were treated using the mean. The data analysis revealed high job satisfaction among public school teachers regarding security, with an overall mean score of 4.3. It suggests that teachers expressed agreement and satisfaction with the pay they receive for their work ($\bar{x} = 4.7$). While there was a moderate agreement regarding the opportunity for reclassification or promotion ($\bar{x} = 3.8$), teachers generally perceived the benefits they receive as competitive compared to other organizations ($\bar{x} = 3.7$). Moreover, teachers demonstrated their commitment to their work by continuing to put in effort even when not fully rewarded ($\bar{x} = 4.0$). They expressed a sense of security regarding the future provided by their job ($\bar{x} = 4.3$) and felt satisfied when their work was acknowledged and credited ($\bar{x} = 4.4$). Teachers took pride in a job well done ($\bar{x} = 4.3$) and expressed happiness with the comparability of their pay to similar jobs in other companies ($\bar{x} = 4.5$) and to their co-workers within the school ($\bar{x} = 4.7$). They also perceived opportunities for advancement positively ($\bar{x} = 4.7$).

Overall, the data analysis highlights job satisfaction among public school teachers, particularly concerning security. Teachers express contentment with their pay and demonstrate dedication to their work, even when rewards are not fully realized. They also feel secure about their future within the profession and derive satisfaction from recognition of their efforts. Additionally, teachers take pride in their accomplishments and perceive opportunities for advancement positively.

Table 9. *The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in terms of Security*

<i>Security (Salary, Benefits, Rewards Performance, Recognition, Promotion)</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
Receive a sufficient amount of pay for the work.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Look forward to the chance to be reclassified/promoted.	3.8	Agree
Still work even if all the efforts are not rewarded.	4.0	Agree
Secure that the job provides a secure future.	4.3	Agree
Primarily satisfied in getting full credit for the work.	4.4	Agree
Can take pride in a job well done.	4.3	Agree
Happy with how the pay compared to a similar job in other companies.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Happy with the pay compared to other school co-workers.	4.7	Strongly Agree
The opportunities for advancement.	4.6	Agree
Total	4.3	Agree

3.8. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in terms of Work Environment

Table 10 presents the level of job satisfaction of public-school teachers in terms of work environment. The data gathered were treated using the mean.

The data analysis revealed high job satisfaction among public school teachers regarding their work environment. With a mean score of 3.95, teachers expressed agreement and satisfaction with the school's policies and practices towards the employees ($\bar{x} = 4.7$). They also reported a positive relationship with their immediate head, appreciating their mutual understanding ($\bar{x} = 4.5$). While co-workers' cooperation level was moderate ($\bar{x} = 3.4$), teachers found it easy to establish friendships with their colleagues ($\bar{x} = 3.5$). They expressed contentment with the working conditions, including heating, lighting, and ventilation ($\bar{x} = 3.7$). Teachers valued the training provided by their immediate head to subordinates ($\bar{x} = 4.1$) and felt a sense of accomplishment from their job ($\bar{x} = 3.7$). They also appreciated how their immediate head addressed employees' complaints ($\bar{x} = 4.1$) and found the overall working conditions pleasant ($\bar{x} = 3.7$). Furthermore, teachers praised the support provided by their immediate superiors when faced with complex problems ($\bar{x} = 4.2$).

Table 10. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in Terms of Work Environment

<i>Work Environment (Policies, Organizational Structures, Physical, Emotional)</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
At the present job, this is how they feel about it.		
Satisfied with the policies and practices of the school employees.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Like how immediately head and undertand each other.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Feel the spiiirit of cooperation among th co-workers.	3.4	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Love the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, and others)	3.7	Agree
Co-workers are easy to make friends.	3.5	Agree
Like the way the immediate head trains their subordinates.	4.1	Agree
Love the feeling of accomplishment from the job.	3.7	Agree
Like how the immediate head takes care of the concerns of their employees.	4.1	Agree
Like the pleasantness of the working conditions.	3.7	Agree
Like the way the immediate superior provides help on complex problems.	4.2	Agree
Total	3.95	Agree

3.9. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in Terms of Job Responsibilities

Table 11 presents the level of job satisfaction of public-school teachers in terms of job responsibilities. The data gathered were treated using the mean.

Data revealed that the level of job satisfaction of public-school teachers in terms of job responsibilities was very high, as shown by the overall mean of 4.53, which means that the teachers could freely rub elbows with important people ($\bar{x}=4.5$). Able to do things that do not go against the conscience ($\bar{x}=3.4$). Have the chance to do work well suited to the abilities ($\bar{x}=4.2$). Can tell other co-workers how to do things ($\bar{x}=4.7$). The chance to try something different in the job. ($\bar{x}=4.6$). Can use abilities at work ($\bar{x}=4.9$). Have a chance to develop new and better ways to do the job ($\bar{x}=4.9$). Have the chance to do things that do not harm the other co-workers ($\bar{x}=4.7$). Have the freedom to use judgment ($\bar{x}=4.7$). Have the chance to do the job without the feeling I am cheating anyone ($\bar{x}=4.8$).

Table 11. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers im Terms of Job Responsibilities.

<i>Job Responsibilities</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
At the present job, this is how they feel about it.		
Could freely rub elbows with important people.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Can do things that do not go againsts the conscience.	3.4	Agree
Have the chance to do work well suited to their abilities.	4.2	Agree
Can tell other co-workers how to do things.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Chance to try something different in the job.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Can use the abilities at work.	4.9	Strongly Agree
A chance to develop new and better ways to do the job.	4.9	Strongly Agree
Can do things that do not harm the other co-workers.	4.7	Stromgly Agree
Have the freedom to use judgement.	4.7	Strongly Agree
The chance to get a job without the feeling of cheating anyone.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Total	4.5	Strongly Agree

3.10. The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in terms of Community Attachments/Linkages

Table 12 presents the level of job satisfaction of public school teachers in terms of community attachments/linkages. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data analysis revealed high job satisfaction among public school teachers regarding their community attachments and linkages, with an overall mean score of 4.53, suggesting that teachers expressed strong agreement and happiness with their sense of belonging in the community ($\bar{x} = 4.3$). They also reported satisfaction with the opportunity to provide small services to others ($\bar{x} = 4.4$) and actively encouraged stakeholders' participation in school activities ($\bar{x} = 3.9$). Teachers felt fulfilled in their role within the community and appreciated the chance to make a difference ($\bar{x} = 4.1$). Their engagement in community outreach programs, such as Linis Barangay, coastal clean-up, and tree planting, was valuable ($\bar{x} = 3.7$), reflecting their dedication to addressing community concerns ($\bar{x} = 3.5$). The

data also highlighted a strong linkage between the school and the immediate community ($\bar{x} = 4.1$), and teachers found satisfaction when their immediate superiors effectively addressed parents' complaints ($\bar{x} = 3.7$). Additionally, teachers were content with the overall positive and supportive atmosphere of the school community towards external stakeholders ($\bar{x} = 4.6$) and acknowledged the social position their profession afforded them in the community ($\bar{x} = 4.5$).

Table 12. *The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in Terms of Community Attachments/Linkages*

<i>Community Attachments/Linkages</i>	<i>Mean n=75</i>	<i>Description</i>
At the present job, this is how they feel about it.		
Happy with the chance to have a definite place in the community.	4.3	Agree
Satisfied with the opportunity to be of some small service to others.	4.4	Agree
Happy with the chance to encourage the stakeholder's participation in all school related activities.	3.9	Agree
Satisfied with the chance to do the community outreach programs (i.e Linis Barangay, coastal clean-up, tree planting)	3.7	Agree
Happy with the chance to help people's concern in the community.	3.5	Agree
There is a strong linkage between the school and the immediate community.	4.1	Agree
Satisfied with the immediate head takes care of some parents' complaints in the community.	4.1	Agree
Content with the pleasantness of the school community towards external stakeholders.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Satisfied with the social positions in the community that goes with the job.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Total	4.63	Strongly Agree

3.11. The Extent of Learners' Behavior in terms of Competence Motivation

Table 13 presents the data on the extent of manifestation of learners' behavior regarding competence motivation. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the extent of the learner's behavior in terms of competence motivation was manifested most of the time, as shown in the overall mean of 3.57. It indicates that the extent of the learner's behavior was manifested most of the time. Learners demonstrated a lively interest in learning activities, with a mean score of 3.5. They cooperated sensibly in class activities, scoring an average of 3.7. They showed a willingness to accept new tasks without fear, scoring an average of 3.4, but occasionally took refuge in dullness or incompetence, with a mean score of 3.5. Learners hesitated about giving answers and sometimes gave up quickly, scoring an average of 3.5. Some learners displayed a don't-care attitude toward success, with a mean score of 3.8, while others showed little desire to please the teacher, scoring an average of 3.5. They were sometimes reluctant to tackle tasks, scoring an average of 3.6. However, most of the time, learners responded in a manner that showed attention, with a mean score of 3.7. Some learners needed more energy or effort in their interest, scoring an average of 3.5. They occasionally delayed answering and waited for hints, scoring an average of 3.7. Furthermore, learners sometimes perceived tasks as too challenging without putting in effort, scoring an average of 3.8, but generally stuck to their tasks with minor distractions, with a mean score of 3.5. It was important to note that these behaviors were mainly observed and may vary among individual learners.

The data indicate that learners' behavior, particularly regarding competence motivation, was predominantly evident, as reflected by an overall mean score of 3.57. Learners showed consistent interest and cooperation in learning activities, although occasional hesitation and reluctance were noted. While some displayed a lack of energy or effort at times, most responded attentively to tasks. Recognizing that these behaviors were observed frequently but may vary among individual learners which is crucial.

Table 13. *The Extent of Learner's Behavior in Terms of Competence Motivation*

<i>Competence Motivation</i>	<i>Mean n=124</i>	<i>Description</i>
Lively interested in learning activities	3.5	Often
Cooperates sensibly in class activities	3.7	Often
Accepts new tasks with no fear	3.4	Sometimes
Takes refuge in dullness/incompetence	3.5	Often
Hesitant to give an answer.	3.5	Often
Gives up easily	3.3	Sometimes
Don't care attitude toward success	3.8	Often
Little desire to please the teacher	3.5	Often
Reluctant to tackle	3.6	Often
Respond in a manner that shows attention	3.7	Often
Too unenergetic for interest/effort	3.5	Often
Delays answer, wait for hint	3.7	Often
Says task too hard without effort	3.8	Often
Sticks to ask with minor distraction	3.5	Often
Total	3.57	Often

3.12. The Extent of Learners' Behavior in terms of Strategy/Flexibility

Table 14 presents the data on the extent of manifestation of learners' behavior regarding strategy/flexibility. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the extent of the learner's behavior manifested most of the time in terms of strategy/flexibility, as shown in the overall mean of 3.48. It suggests that learners exhibited behaviors such as inventing silly ways to do tasks, with a mean score of 3.2, and occasionally displaying hostility when frustrated or corrected, receiving a mean score of 3.0. They also demonstrated enterprising ideas that only sometimes worked out, with a mean score of 3.4, and occasionally performed tasks in their own way, scoring an average of 3.5. Some learners exhibited peculiar or inflexible procedures, scoring an average of 3.5, while others used their charm to persuade others to do their work, with a mean score of 3.3. Additionally, learners occasionally fidgeted, squirmed, or left their seats, scoring an average of 4.2. Some learners reported headaches and pains as a means to avoid learning, with a mean score of 3.4, while others acknowledged that their productivity was affected when they were in a bad mood, scoring an average of 3.6. Lastly, some learners easily got distracted or actively sought out distractions, scoring an average of 3.7.

Table 14. *The Extent of Learners' Behavior in Terms of Strategy/Flexibility*

<i>Strategy Flexibility</i>	<i>Mean n=124</i>	<i>Description</i>
Invests silly ways to do tasks	3.2	Often
Hostile when frustrated or corrected	3.0	Sometimes
Enterprising ideas that do not work	3.4	Sometimes
Performs own not accepted way	3.5	Often
Peculiar/inflexible procedures	3.5	Often
Charms others to do work	3.3	Sometimes
Fidget/squirms leaves the seat	4.2	Often
Headaches and pains to avoid learning	3.4	Sometimes
Does not work well in a bad mood	3.6	Often
Distracted easily or seeks distraction	3.7	Often
Total	3.48	Sometimes

3.13. Significant Relationship between Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction

Table 15 presents the significant relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to handle the collected data.

It was found that when the teaching performance and job satisfaction levels were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 122. The table shows that Pearson's computed Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.78. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. The level of teaching performance practices significantly influenced the level of job satisfaction.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship between Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>rXY Value</i> <i>n=124</i>		<i>Decision</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
		<i>Computed</i>	<i>Tabular</i>		
Teaching Performance VS Job Satisfaction	122	0.78	0.175	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.14. Significant Relationship between Teaching Performance and Learners' Behavior

Table 16 presents the significant relationship between teaching performance and learners' behavior. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to handle the collected data.

When the degree of teaching performance and the extent of learners' behavior were examined, the data were tested at the Alpha level. 05 with a difference of 122. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. The level of teaching performance significantly influenced the extent of learners' behavior

Table 16. *Significant Relationships Between Training Performance and Learners Behavior*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>rXY Value</i> <i>n=124</i>		<i>Decision</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
		<i>Computed</i>	<i>Tabular</i>		
Teaching Performance VS Learners Behavior	122	0.79	0.175	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.14. Significant Relationship between Learners' Behavior and Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers

Table 17 presents the significant relationship between learners' behavior and job satisfaction of public school teachers. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to handle the collected data.

It was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level. 05 with a difference of 122 when the degree of job satisfaction and the extent of learners' conduct were examined. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.77, as the table demonstrates. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. The level extent of learners' behavior significantly influenced job satisfaction.

Table 17. Significant Relationships Between Learner's Behavior and Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers

Variables	Df	r _{XY} Value n=124		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Teaching Behavior VS Job Satisfaction	122	0.77	0.175	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.15. On the Mediating Effect of Learner's Behavior

Table 18 shows the path analysis of the mediating effect of learner's behavior on the relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction.

The data revealed the direct effect of teaching performance and job satisfaction, teaching performance and learner's behavior, and learner's behavior and job satisfaction. Teaching performance and job satisfaction are the paths with an unstandardized regression coefficient of .912, standardized regression coefficient of .844, S.E. of .029, and a probability value of less than 0.05. A low or tiny standard error indicates that the estimate was more accurate, and below the significance level of 0.05 suggests that these two variables have a meaningful link. The impact of efficiency, or effect size was 95%, which is significant enough to disprove the null hypothesis. Moreover, the path b coefficient, which is teaching performance and learner's behavior has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .096, standardized regression coefficient of .112, S.E. of .050, and a p-value of .018, which was lower than the significance alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the relationship between teaching performance and learner's behavior was significant. The effect size of teaching performance and learner's behavior is 8%.

Lastly, the path c coefficient reveals the effect size of learner's behavior and job satisfaction. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .714 or 74% efficiency, a standardized regression coefficient of .801; the computed standard error is .014, and a p-value smaller than 0.05, meaning the two variables have a significant relationship. Mathematically, this supports the assumption that the learner's behavior is associated with the teacher's job satisfaction. Overall, these findings suggest meaningful connections between teaching performance, learner's behavior, and job satisfaction in the educational context.

Table 18. Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)

PATH	Estimates		SE	C.R.	P
	Understandardized	Standardized			
Teaching Performance Job Satisfaction	.912	.844	.029	27.124	***
Teaching Performance Learner's Behavior	.096	.112	.050	2.277	.019
Learner's Behavior Job Satisfaction	.714	.801	0.19	16.002	***

Discussion

This section presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the data gathered.

The Level of Teaching Performance of Public School Teachers in Terms Of Content, Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity Of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development.

The level of teaching performance of public-school teachers was very high in terms of content, knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, personal growth and professional development while agreeing on the diversity of learners, community linkages, and professional engagement.

Public school teachers' teaching performance in content, knowledge, and pedagogy was very high. Based on the responses provided, the evaluated teachers have a strong proficiency in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. They possess a deep understanding of the content areas they teach and utilize research-based principles of teaching and learning to enhance their professional practice. Additionally, they effectively communicate in the language of instruction, using various strategies to support students' understanding,

participation, engagement, and achievement. They also apply teaching strategies that promote critical and creative ideas and other higher-order thinking skills. Overall, they have demonstrated high proficiency in their teaching practice.

This assumption parallels to the study of Arens et al. (2021), which found that effective pedagogy is critical to engaging students, creating a positive classroom environment, and fostering a love of learning. Teachers should use various teaching methods that cater to different learning styles and abilities. Strong content knowledge is also essential, enabling teachers to develop effective pedagogical strategies that meet their students' needs and deepen their understanding.

Moreover, the level of teaching performance of public school teachers was very high in terms of learning environment, indicating that they perform excellently. Teachers being evaluated have demonstrated strong proficiency in creating a positive learning environment by consistently implementing policies, guidelines, and procedures and promoting fairness, respect, and care. They engage learners in meaningful exploration and hands-on activities within various physical learning environments, maintain supportive and inspiring learning environments, and apply successful strategies to motivate learners to assume responsibility for their learning. They also manage learner's behavior constructively through positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning remains the focus. Overall, they possess a high level of proficiency in creating and maintaining a learning-focused environment that enhances students' learning.

This assumption parallels to the study of Imron et al. (2020), which states that teacher commitment is an internal force that motivates instructors to continue their involvement in the school by devoting more time and effort to it. This readiness to support the school fosters an emotional bond between the instructors and the institution. It motivates them to look for methods to advance their careers as teachers and create a productive learning environment that enables students to achieve their goals.

Further, the teaching performance of public school teachers was high in terms of the diversity of learners. They demonstrated strong proficiency in creating a diverse learning atmosphere that is responsive to the needs of all learners. They use differentiated learning experiences that are developmentally appropriate and respond to the strengths, interests, and experiences of the learners. They establish a learner-centered culture responsive to learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds. They also design, adapt, and implement teaching methods that accommodate to the needs of the students with disabilities, giftedness, and talents. They have individual plans and delivers teaching strategies that address the special educational needs of the learners under challenging circumstances and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies for learners from Indigenous groups. This assumption was parallel to the study of Pennington and Richards (2016), who found that these factors, as well as cultural and linguistic backgrounds, also influence the behavior of the learners. Students from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds may have different learning styles, values, and beliefs. Therefore, teachers need to be culturally responsive and understand the diversity of their students.

Furthermore, the teaching performance of public school teachers was very high in terms of curriculum and planning. Teachers demonstrated strong proficiency in curriculum and planning. They plan and implement developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes that meet the curriculum requirements and adapt learning programs to respond to the needs of all learners. They set appropriate learning outcomes aligned with learning competencies and use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice. The individual selects and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning objectives. Overall, they possess a high level of proficiency in curriculum and planning, which is essential for ensuring effective teaching and learning. This assumption parallels to the study of Martin et al. (2019), a critical aspect of effective curriculum and planning, an alignment with learning goals and standards. Teachers should clearly understand what students are expected to learn and the standards or benchmarks they must meet. Effective planning involves designing activities aligned with these learning goals and standards that help students achieve the intended outcomes.

In addition, the level of teaching performance of public school teachers was very high in assessment and reporting. Teachers demonstrated a strong proficiency in assessment and reporting. They design, select, organize, and use appropriate assessment strategies that align with curriculum requirements. They monitor and evaluate learners' progress using attainment data, provide timely and constructive feedback, and communicate learners' needs and progress to key stakeholders. They also use assessment data to modify teaching and learning practices and programs. Overall, they possess a high proficiency in assessment and reporting, which is crucial for improving learners' outcomes and ensuring effective teaching and learning. This assumption parallels to the study of Bonner et al. (2018). Their research suggests that practical assessment and reporting can improve students' achievement, motivation, and engagement. Teachers who use various assessment methods, provide timely feedback, and use evaluation data to inform instruction which can help students develop deeper thinking of the subject matter and enhance their learning outcomes.

Likewise, the level of teaching performance of public school teachers was high in terms of community linkages and professional engagement. They cultivate relationships with parents, guardians, and the larger school community to encourage participation in the educational process and maintain learning settings sensitive to community circumstances. Using current laws and rules about the teaching profession and the obligations posed in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, they periodically evaluate their methods of instruction. Additionally, they consistently follow school regulations and procedures to promote positive connections with students, parents, and other stakeholders. Overall, they has demonstrated a strong proficiency in community linkages and professional engagement, essential for building positive relationships with the school community and ensuring effective teaching and learning.

This assumption parallels to the study of Scales et al. (2020). Effective community linkages and professional engagement can improve

students' achievement, engagement, and motivation. Teachers with strong connections with families, communities, and other professionals can create a more supportive and engaging learning environment for their students. Similarly, ongoing professional development and collaboration with colleagues can help teachers enhance their instructional practices and better meet the diverse needs of their students.

Additionally, the level of teaching performance of public school teachers was very high in terms of personal growth and professional development. They apply a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered and exhibit qualities such as a caring attitude, respect, and integrity, which upholds the dignity of teaching as a profession. They participate in professional networks to share knowledge and enhance practice and develop a personal improvement plan based on reflection on their practice and ongoing professional learning. They also set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Overall, they demonstrated a strong proficiency in personal growth and professional development, which is essential for ensuring ongoing growth and development in the teaching profession.

This assumption parallels to the study of Cocca et al. (2018). They suggest that effective personal growth and professional development can improve student achievement, engagement, and motivation. Teachers who engage in ongoing personal and professional development can improve their instructional practices, learn about new technologies and teaching strategies, and better meet their students' changing needs.

The Level of Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in Terms Of Security, Work Environment, Job Responsibilities, and Community Attachments/Linkages

The level of job satisfaction of public school teachers was high in terms of security and work environment and very high in terms of job responsibilities and community attachments/linkages.

They positively perceived their job security in terms of salary, benefits, rewards, performance, recognition, and promotion. They strongly agree that they receive sufficient pay for their work and are happy with their pay compares to other school co-workers. They also strongly agree that opportunities for advancement are available, and they feel secure that their job provides a secure future. Additionally, they agree that their benefits are good and they can take pride in a well-done job. However, they also agree that they still work even when all their efforts are not rewarded. Overall, they demonstrated a positive perception of their job security and compensation, essential for ensuring job satisfaction and motivation in teaching.

This assumption parallels to Deng's study (2020). Security is an essential aspect of any organization, and measures must be in place to protect the organization's assets and information from internal and external threats. To ensure that workers are driven to perform their best in this critical area, competitive salaries, benefits, rewards, recognition, and promotion opportunities must be offered.

Moreover, the level of job satisfaction of public school teachers in terms of work environment was high. The work environment is generally positive and conducive to job satisfaction, with satisfactory policies and practices towards the employees, good supervision from the immediate head, and satisfactory working conditions. The feeling of accomplishment is appreciated, and the immediate head is responsive to employees' complaints, provides help on complex problems, and trains the subordinates satisfactorily. However, there is sometimes a need for more cooperation among co-workers, although they are generally friendly. This assumption parallels to the study of Rasool et al. (2021), who stated that a positive work environment can contribute to employees' satisfaction, productivity, and engagement, while a hostile work environment can lead to stress, burnout, and turnover. Factors that can influence the work environment include the company's mission and values, the leadership style of managers, the quality of relationships among colleagues, and the physical design of the workspace.

Additionally, the level of job satisfaction of public school teachers in terms of job responsibilities was very high. The job responsibilities, duties, and moral/ethical considerations are all positively perceived. Individuals can interact with influential people, work well-suited to their abilities, and try new things. They can also use their abilities and develop new and better ways to do the job while considering their co-workers and not compromising their conscience. They are free to use their judgment and do the job without feeling like cheating anyone. Overall, the job duties were really fulfilling and widely accepted.

This assumption parallels to the study of Demirkol and Nalla (2018), which found that job responsibilities are one of the five core job characteristics that influence work motivation, satisfaction, and performance. A meaningful job responsibility that requires various skills and task identity promotes higher job satisfaction and performance levels. In contrast, monotonous and low-autonomy job responsibilities can lead to boredom and disengagement.

Furthermore, the level of job satisfaction of public school teachers in terms of community attachments/linkages was very high. They feel positively connected to their community through their job. They are happy with their place in the community and have the opportunity to provide small services and help with community concerns. They are also satisfied with the chance to encourage the stakeholders participation and do community outreach programs. There is a strong linkage between the school and the community. They are contented with the pleasantness towards external stakeholders. They are also satisfied with the social position that comes with the job. The relationships and ties within the community were very fulfilling and widely acknowledged. This assumption parallels to the study of Grant et al. (2019), which states that community attachments can also facilitate economic development and social capital.

A study of rural communities found that community attachments were a crucial factor in promoting entrepreneurship and economic development. Moreover, social capital - the resources and connections that individuals and groups have entry through their social networks - can be enhanced by strong community attachments.

The extent of learners' behavior in terms of competence motivation and Strategy/Flexibility

The extent of learners' behavior in terms of competence motivation was often and sometimes in terms of strategy/flexibility.

The extent of learners' behavior in terms of competence motivation was manifested most of the time. Learners had prominent competence motivation in showing a lively interest in learning activities, cooperating sensibly in-class activities, and responding in a manner that shows attention. However, they also show tendencies towards being hesitant about giving answers, giving up easily, having a don't-care attitude towards success, and having little desire to please the teacher. They are often reluctant to tackle new tasks and may take refuge in dullness/incompetence. Additionally, they may delay answering and wait for hints or say a task is too complex without putting an effort. They tend to stick to tasks even with minor distractions.

This assumption parallels to the study of Józsa and Barrett (2018). Competence motivation is also linked to learners' self-efficacy beliefs, which refer to their belief in their skills to succeed in a particular task or situation. Individuals with high self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to approach challenging tasks with positive behavior and engage in self-regulated learning behaviors.

The extent of learners' behavior in terms of competence motivation was manifested occasionally. Learners can adapt to changing circumstances and take different approaches to problem-solving. Based on the provided data, they exhibit positive and negative behaviors, including creativity, resistance to established procedures, difficulty handling frustration, a tendency to be distracted, and a need for emotional regulation. The total score of 3.48 suggests that these behaviors are exhibited sometimes. They may benefit from developing emotional regulation skills, seeking diverse perspectives, and practicing focus and concentration techniques to improve adaptability.

This assumption parallels to the study of Huang et al. (2020). Strategy and flexibility are two interrelated concepts that have important implications for learning and problem-solving. Developing and using effective strategies are crucial for academic success, while flexibility enables the learners to adapt their strategies in response to changing circumstances.

Significant relationship between Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction

The test of the relationship between variables shows a significant relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction, implying that the level of teaching performance practices is associated with job satisfaction. It was found that the level of teaching performance practices was compared to the level of job satisfaction. The data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference (df) of 122. The table revealed that the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.78. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. The level of teaching performance practices significantly influenced the level of job satisfaction. This assumption parallels to the study of Toropova et al. (2021), who suggest a strong relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction. Teachers who feel satisfied with their work are more likely to be motivated, participate, and committed to their teaching practice. In turn, this can lead to improved teaching performance and better student outcomes.

Significant Relationship between Teaching Performance and Learners' Behavior

The test of the relationship between the variables disclosed a significant relationship between teaching performance and learners' behavior, implying that teaching performance is associated with job satisfaction. It was found that when the level of teaching performance was compared to the extent of the learner's behavior, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a value of 122. The table revealed that the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to the refusal of the null hypothesis. The level of teaching performance significantly influenced the extent of learners' behavior. This assumption parallels the study of Gracia and Weiss (2019). The relationship between teaching performance and learners' behavior is an essential area of education research. Teaching performance refers to the quality of teaching teachers provide to their students.

In contrast, learners' behavior refers to how students interact with their teachers, peers, and learning environment. Research suggests a strong relationship between teaching performance and learners' behavior. Teachers who provide high-quality instruction are likelier to create a positive and supportive learning atmosphere, enhancing students' behavior and engagement.

Significant Relationship between Learners' Behavior and Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers

The test of the relationship between the variables disclosed a significant relationship between learners' behavior and the job satisfaction of public school teachers. It implies that the extent of learners' behavior was compared to the level of job satisfaction; the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 122. The table revealed that the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.77. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.175, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. The extent of learners' behavior significantly influenced job satisfaction. This assumption parallels to the study of Toropova (2021). Learners' behavior refers to how students interact with their teachers, peers, and learning environment, while job satisfaction refers to

the level of contentment that teachers experience in their work. Research suggests a strong relationship exists between learners' behavior and the job satisfaction of public school teachers.

On the Mediating Effect of Learner's Behavior

The path analysis indicates that Teaching Performance and Learner Behavior have distinct relationships with Job Satisfaction. Higher Teaching Performance contributes to increased Job Satisfaction among teachers, while positive Learners' Behavior also positively influences their overall job satisfaction. These findings elucidate the importance of effective teaching practices and positive learners' engagement in fostering job satisfaction among educators. This assumption parallels to the study of Cocca et al. (2018), who stated that teachers who perceive themselves as effective educators, receiving positive feedback and recognition, tend to experience higher job satisfaction. Conversely, teachers who struggle with classroom management or perceive themselves as ineffective may experience lower level of job satisfaction, which can impact their overall teaching performance

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated: First, the level of teaching performance of teachers was very high in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development, while high in terms of diversity of learners, and community linkages and professional engagement. Second, teachers' job satisfaction was very high regarding job responsibilities and community attachments/linkages. Third, the extent of the learner's behavior manifested most of the time in competence and motivation, while occasionally manifested in strategy/flexibility.

Additionally, there was a significant relationship between the level of teaching performance and job satisfaction, teaching performance and extent of learner's behavior, and the extent of learner's behavior and the level of job satisfaction. Lastly, there was a partial effect of teaching performance and job satisfaction, teaching performance and learner's behavior, and learner's behavior and job satisfaction.

Based on the study's results, the following recommendations were established: The Department of Education may provide teacher's training and professional development programs. These initiatives can enhance their teaching skills, keep them updated with the new pedagogical techniques, and help them effectively manage learners' behavior. Teachers feeling equipped and confident in their abilities can positively impact their job satisfaction. The Division Superintendent can consider implementing evidence-based strategies such as positive reinforcement, modeling, and social skills training.

School administrators may implement a teacher evaluation system that provides constructive feedback to teachers to improve their teaching performance. School heads may support teachers in implementing effective classroom management techniques that address different learners' behaviors. Equip them with tools and strategies to handle diverse students' needs, maintain discipline, and create a positive learning environment, contributing to better teaching performance and increased job satisfaction. Teachers may assess learners' behavior through evaluations, classroom observations, and students' feedback. Lastly, future researcher may use the study results to enhance their interest and skills in research and help as a guideline to those who plan to conduct research relevant to the study.

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